

ENHANCING LEARNERS' MASTERY IN USING THE DEGREES OF ADJECTIVES IN MAKING COMPARISONS THROUGH *BITUIN ENLIGHTENS ADJECTIVES*

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ABSTRACT

Enhancing learners' mastery in comparing using the degree of comparison of adjective and their academic performance through a Strategic Intervention Material "Bituin Enlightens Adjective" was investigated in this study. The respondents of the study were the grade three learners of Lupigue Integrated School. This action research utilized pretest-posttest quasi- experimental design to carry out the study. This research design was characterized by having two groups of students, one group was exposed to the intervention material and identified as the experimental group, while the other group served as the control group where the learners were not exposed in the intervention. The experimental group utilized the SIM, and a traditional way of teaching was implemented for control group. After the treatment, both groups were given posttest. Based, from the result of the findings on the treated data gathered, there is a significant effect on the use of SIM to the enhancement of the mastery level of the grade 3 learners in making comparisons using the degree of adjective. This goes to show that SIM is an effective tool in increasing the academic performance of the learners.

Keywords: *strategic intervention material, quasi- experimental design, pretest-posttest, degree of comparison, SIM, enhancing learners' mastery, Grade 3, Aggabao*

INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education has its battle cry, “No learners should be left behind” in terms of quality education as stated in the Education for All (EFA) goal. Furthermore, it is also constitutionally mandated to provide every Filipino learner not only access to complete basic education but quality education that promotes equality, equity and culture-based education as also stated in the department’s mission. For us to bring the quality of education in to the higher level, curriculum specialists provide every learner sufficient time to master and apply the key concepts and skills to develop a lifelong and globally competent learners through arranging the competencies in a spiral progression manner. Furthermore, with the willingness and determination to take Filipino Education be abreast with changes, the department come up with a movement to address the gap towards quality education to every Filipino learner with the slogan “Sulong EduKalidad”. This program is the department’s move to innovate Philippine education in response to a ‘world drastically changing.

Maximum delivery of quality education happens inside every classroom. A place where learners are motivated and facilitated to develop their full potential and in the hands of the teachers, being the frontrunners in the field of education lies the realization of the Department’s Mission and Vision in delivering quality education that will help them to become globally competitive citizens.

In the Philippine Educational System, the use of English is one of the primary medium of instruction. Consequently, learning the language is an essential part for every learner since a medium of communication and learning goes hand by hand (Alieto, 2018) Usually, parents already taught their child vocabulary words before they enter nursery. Furthermore, the role of English in delivering quality education is equally important as the other fields such as Science, Mathematics and other subjects. The subject itself is a way to improve the primary instrument of thoughts which is communication skills and it is the center of intellectual, social and emotional development. Thus, English has an invaluable role across all learning areas. (Balido, 2019)

In the K to 12 curriculum, English comprises domains of listening comprehension, viewing comprehension, vocabulary development, literature, writing and composition, oral language and fluency, reading comprehension and grammar awareness. These domains are all components needed to attain the maximum understanding of the subject matters in other learning areas (Balido, 2019)

Unfortunately, teachers today are in midst of agony against different sets of challenges inside their class brought about by diversity of learnings styles, interest, needs and habits. Furthermore, the students’ itself has the hesitation of speaking English and learning the English subject. With this, in the teachers’ shoulder lie the responsibilities of introducing and letting the students use the language.

With the eagerness to assess the English performance of Filipino learners, the Department of Education joined the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) last 2018, the country only got 357 points that does not even make it to Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development average of 489 that made it ranked in the low 70's in reading, science, and mathematics (PISA 2018). These indicates that there is a need to address the gap in improving the learners' performance in terms of English.

The Regional Memorandum issued last May 24, 2019 with regards to the 2018 National Achievement Test Results and Analysis showed that English has a low performance with a mean percentage score of 35.49%. These data showed that there is a need to address these performances since it falls under Average Mastery since all the mean percentage does not meet the national standard level of acceptable mean percentage of 75%. This does specifically point out the specific domain of English that made the performance low, however the researcher claims based from her observation that the Grade 3 learners has difficulty in using the degrees of adjectives in making comparisons. It just part of the whole, however, the degree of adjectives is important element in sentence. Using it can help us to express the quality of any person or object. In addition, it made writings more visual and vivid. With this, readers will get a better idea of what we wish them to picture when they are reading. It appeals to our readers' senses.

This claim was proven in the result of the summative test item analysis of English Grade 3 learners. The data reflected that learners found it hard to use adjectives in making comparisons. Furthermore, the teachers observed that students find it difficult to master the concept of the competency.

It was for this reason that the researcher developed and constructed Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) in English 3 to enhance learning and increase the mastery level of the learners to the least mastered competency. In the blog of by Sunstar Pampanga (2017), it is stated that, SIM helps the learners develop competencies that they did not master during regular classes. According to different studies teaching at any level requires the students to be exposed at some form of stimulation or intervention to improve academic achievement. Learners can learn faster and easier if they are given the chance to learn through more senses than one.

And since the material is contextually and locally made, it brings into consideration the capacities and abilities of the student-clientele, use locally known materials and culture, and makes learning experience more personal

Thus, this SIM was believed to improve the mastery of the learners on using adjectives in making comparisons.

Research Questions

This action research was envisioned in finding out the effectiveness of Bituin Enlightens Adjectives improving the performance and mastery level of the Grade 3 learners' of

Lupigue Integrated School in the specified competency. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following:

1. What is the level of learners' academic performance on the topic Using Degrees of Adjectives in Making Comparisons on the Control and Experimental groups before and after the utilization of SIM?
2. Is there a significant mean difference between the learners' academic performance on the topic Adjectives in Making Comparisons on Experimental group before and after the utilization of SIM?
3. Is there a significant mean difference between the learners' academic performance on the topic Adjectives in Making Comparisons on the Control and Experimental groups after the utilization of SIM?

METHODOLOGY

a. Participants and/or other Sources of Data and Information

This action research was conducted at Lupigue Integrated School on September 2022 and employed quasi-experimental research design. The same research design was also employed in the study of Limbago-Bastida and Bastida (2022) in their study Effectiveness of Strategic Intervention Material on the Learning Outcomes of Learners. In their study, the researchers used control and experimental classes to determining the effectiveness of SIM. The control group were taught using the traditional method, while the group tagged as the experimental group were taught using the SIM.

The respondents of the study were the 2 sections of Grade 3 learners. 25 Grade 3-Masaya learners and the 25 Grade 3- Mapagmalasakit learners, one was exposed to the intervention and the other was not. The main tool to gather data relevant to this research was the administration of competency-based test questionnaire. Class record was also examined by the researcher to verify the test result.

b. Data Gathering Methods

This action research utilized pretest-posttest quasi- experimental design to carry out the study. This research design was characterized by having two groups of students, one group was exposed to the intervention and identified as the experimental group, while the other group served as the control group where the learners was not exposed in the intervention. As cited by Reyes and Falle (2021) in their study, experimental method of research is a method or procedure involving the control or manipulation of conditions for the purpose of studying the relative effects of various treatments applied to members of a sample, or of the same treatment applied to members of different samples. After the conduct of the quarterly examination, the researcher identified the least mastered

competency through the use of test item analysis. Subsequently, after determining the least mastered competency, the researcher conducted pre-test to learners. The least mastered competencies were used as bases for constructing the SIM as an intervention material.

Thereafter the conduct of SIM for two weeks in a 50- minute intensive intervention for experimental group. The students were properly guided and instructed on how to use the said material. On the other hand, 50- minute conventional or traditional way of teaching was implemented for control group daily. After the treatment, both sections were given posttest. This was the basis in determining the academic performance of the learners.

c. Data Analysis Plan

The data gathered in this study were tabulated, treated, analyzed and used as bases for interpretation. Standard statistical procedures and formula were used to arrive at a reliable conclusion. The researcher used Mean, Minimum, Maximum Value, Mean Percentage Score (MPS) as statistical treatment to process the data and to arrive at descriptive interpretation of each item in the instrument. Paired t-test was employed to compare the two mean scores after the implementation of SIM and lastly, an Independent T-Test was also employed to get the significant difference in the post-test scores of the two groups.

RESULTS

1. What is the level of learners' academic performance on the control and experimental groups before the utilization of the SIM?

Table 1. Pre-test before the utilization of SIM

Group	Number of Learners	Minimum Score	Maximum Score	Mean - Score	Mean Percentage Score
Control Group	25	5	14	9.68	48%
Experimental Group	25	5	13	9.52	47.60%

Table 1 represents the statistical data on the level of achievement before the integration of SIM. The data provides the summation scores of the two groups, minimum and maximum scores, mean score, and mean percentage score. Base from the gathered data, respondents in Control Group has minimum and maximum scores of 5 and 14 respectively, while experimental group got 5 and 13. Moreover, control group got a mean score of 9.68 and mean percentage score of 48%. On the other hand, the other group recorded a mean score of 9.52 which also garnered 47.60% mean percentage score.

The mean scores, shows that control group has a higher mean score and mean percentage score compared to the experimental group. Furthermore, the registered mean percentage score of the two groups did not meet the national standard of 75 % proficiency level attributed to all learning areas as set by the DO 73, s. 2012 – Guidelines on the Assessment and Rating of Learning Outcomes Under the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum.

Generally, both groups got an alarming mean percentage score, thus intervention was really needed to aide the learners to uplift their academic performance in the competency. Inadequate materials and resources can result to negative effect on the academic performance of pupils in finishing their performance task and written works, thus, determining the level and quality of students based on the study of Jotia and Matlale as stated by Popoola (1990).

2. What is the level of learners' academic performance on the control and experimental groups after the utilization of the SIM?

Table 2. Post-test Results after the utilization of SIM

Group	Number of Learners	Minimum Score	Maximum Score	Mean - Score	Mean Percentage Score
Control Group	25	5	15	10.2	51%
Experimental Group	25	12	20	18.12	91%

Table 2 shows the statistical data on the level of achievement after the integration of SIM. The data provides the minimum and maximum scores, mean score, standard deviation and mean percentage score of the two groups after the utilization of SIM. Base from the gathered data, respondents in Control Group has minimum and maximum scores of 5 and 15 respectively, while experimental group go 12, and 20. Moreover, control group got a mean score of 10.2 and mean percentage score of 51%. On the other hand, the other group recorded a mean score of 18.12 which also garnered 91% mean percentage score. The mean scores, shows that control group has a lower mean score compared to the experimental group. Furthermore, the registered mean percentage score of the experimental group became higher, having a mean percentage score of 91%, meeting the national standard of 75 % proficiency level attributed to all learning areas set by the DepEd Order no. 73, s. 2012. Guidelines on the Assessment and Rating of Learning Outcomes under the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum.

3. Is there a significant mean difference between the learners' academic performance on the topic Adjectives in Making Comparisons on Experimental group before and after the utilization of SIM?

Table 3. T-test results for pre-test and post-test scores of learners in the utilization of SIM under the experimental and control group

Variable	Computed T-Test Value (Two-Tailed)	P- Value	Remarks
Experimental Group (Pre-test vs. Post-test)	1.67	<.001	Significant
Control Group vs. Experimental Group (Post-test vs. Post-test)	2.11	<.001	Significant

Table 3 reveals the T-test results of the learners in utilization of the SIM as a basis whether there is a significant impact brought by the SIM to the improvement of the academic performance of the learner in competency using the degrees of adjectives in making comparisons. In addition, it also presents the significant difference between the post-test score of both the control and experimental group. It is further revealed that the experimental group pre-test and post-test has a computed value of 1.67 that is lower than the p-value at 1 % level of significance. Moreover, based from the data we can conclude that there is a significant effect on the usage of SIM to the improvements of the academic performance of the Grade 3 Learners in Making Comparison using the Degrees of Adjectives. This goes to show that the difference in the pretest and posttest is significant and implies that SIM is effective tool in increasing the academic performance of the learners. Furthermore, the result of the study is also parallel with the study conducted by Acera (2022), stated that through the use of Strategic Intervention Material learners will be given opportunities and responsibility to be more actively engaged or involved in the progress of their own learning. It was observed that a good number of pupils have shown significant improvement in their academic performance. Thus, the application on the utilization of Strategic Intervention Material was a success.

On the other hand, using the Independent T-Test, the findings show that the two groups comparison on their post-test scores has a computes value of 2.11 which is also lower than the p-value at 1 % level of significance making the claims for the effectiveness of the SIM to be more significant. It also follows that mean scores of experimental groups after exposure to the intervention is larger compared to the control group. The results are also parallel with the study of Arisi et, al (1998) as cited by Casinillo and Suarez (2022) in his study that Strategic Intervention Materials is effective at 1% level of significance. This further means that the implementation of SIM has a positive impact and respond to learners.

DISCUSSION

The following are the findings of this action research.

1. The mean scores of the control group before the implementation of the intervention is 9.68 while their mean score after the implementation is 10.2.
 2. The mean scores of the experimental group before the implementation of the intervention is 9.52 while their mean score after the implementation is 18.12.
 3. The mean percentage score of the control group before the implementation of the intervention is 48% while their mean percentage after the implementation is 51%
 4. The mean percentage score of the experimental group before the implementation of the intervention is 47.60% while their mean percentage after the implementation is 91%.
 5. The experimental group's mean percentage score is 91 %, meeting the 75% of the National's Level of Proficiency.
 6. The computed t-test pre-test and post-test of experimental group is 1.67 which is lower than the p-value of 2.492 at 0. 01 level of significance.
 7. The computed t-test post-test of both groups is 2.11 which is lower than the p-value of 2.492 at 0. 01 level of significance.
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Conclusions

Based from the findings, the following are the conclusions.

1. The posttest mean score of experimental group is higher than posttest score of the control group. Thus, the use of the SIM is effective in enhancing Learners' Mastery in Using the Degrees of Adjectives in Making Comparisons Through Bituin Enlightens Adjectives.
 2. There is a significant difference in the mastery of control and experimental group thus, experimental groups better than the control group. Hence, SIM should be used as intervention to enhance mastery among learners and address difficult topics to be mastered.
 3. The mean percentage score of the learners expose in the intervention met the 75% national proficiency level in all subject areas.
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Recommendations

From the aforementioned findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. SIM should be used in teaching least mastered competencies in Using Degrees of Adjectives in making comparison.

2. Teachers should be given in-service training on how to create SIM for them to gain more knowledge and clear understanding of its uses so that they can provide learners with quality assured learning intervention.
3. School administrations and teachers should be able to maintain and enrich provision of activities for the students to have chance to learn new ideas in English.
4. Researchers in the field of education are encouraged to conduct the same study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The proponent followed the proper action research protocol wherein she seek approval of the proposal to the division office first before gathering data needed. The data gathered and the result of this study was treated with confidentiality and used only for the purpose of this study.

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REFERENCES

- Acera F. (2022). The Use of Strategic Intervention Materials in Improving the Academic Performance of the Learners. Retrieved on September 17, 2024. from at [414665472.pdf \(ijassjournal.com\)](https://www.ijassjournal.com/414665472.pdf)
- Alieto, E. (2018). Language shift from English to Mother Tongue: Exploring language attitude and willingness to teach among pre-service teachers. *TESOL International Journal*, 13(3), 134-146. Retrieved May 25, 2019, from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED602389.pdf>

- Balido G. (2019), "MANGI MODELS MODALS", ITS EFFECTIVENESS IN MASTERING THE COMPETENCIES ON THE USE OF MODALS OF GRADE 10 ENGLISH LEARNERS OF LUPIGUE INTEGRATED SCHOOL"
- Department of Education (2019)., PISA-2018-Philippine-National-Report. Retrieved March 1, 2021 from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/PISA-2018-Philippine-National-Report.pdf>
- DepEd Order no. 73, s. 2012. Guidelines on the Assessment and Rating of Learning Outcomes under the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum. Retrieved on September 19, 2024 from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2012/09/05/do-73-s-2012-guidelines-on-the-assessment-and-rating-of-learning-outcomes-under-the-k-to-12-basic-education-curriculum/>
- Jotia, A. L. and Matlale, O. J. (2011). Use of instructional materials in social studies: Impact on students' performance in primary school leaving certificate examinations in Botswana. *European Journal of Educational Studies*, 3(1), 111-122.
- Limbago-Bastida R.A and Bastida, G. (2022). Effectiveness of Strategic Intervention Material on the Learning Outcomes of Learners. Retrieved September 17, 2024 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/360351315_EFFECTIVENESS_OF_STRATEGIC_INTERVENTION_MATERIAL_ON_THE_LEARNING_OUTCOMES_OF_STUDENTS
- Popoola, T.A. (1990). An investigation into the relationship between instructional resources and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria. An unpublished MEd Thesis.
- Region Office 2 (2019), 2018 National achievement test 6,10, and 12 Results and Analysis. Retrieved March 1, 2021 from <https://region2.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/2018-NATIONAL-ACHIEVEMENT-TEST-NAT-610-12-RESULTS-AND-ANALYSIS-.pdf>
- Reyes, E. and Falle, T. (2021), Strategic Intervention Material: Performance level of Grade 7 students of Zambales National High School Schools Division of Zambales, Philippines. Retrieved March 19, 2020 from <https://uijir.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/10-UIJIR-21517.pdf>
- Suarez M. and Casinillo L. (2022). Effect of Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) on Academic Performance: Evidence from the students of Science IV. Retrieved on January 12, 2023 from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3804203
- Sun Star Pampanga (2017)., Strategic Intervention (SIM) for a Change. Retrieved on January 13, 2023 from <https://www.pressreader.com/>
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